

hypothesis that the migration differences observed for both enzymes are each controlled by a single locus with 2 co-dominant alleles. For IDH, these alleles are Idh¹⁰⁰ and Idh⁹³. For MDH, they

are Mdh¹⁰⁰ and Mdh¹⁰⁹. The heterozygotes for the two alleles at the Idh and Mdh loci had an intermediate band in addition to the parental ones, indicating that IDH and MDH isozymes are dimers.

We also noted the presence of other rare variants for IDH and MDH which could be codominant with the other alleles of each enzyme. □

Oviposition of brown planthopper (BPH) on some common weeds, wild rices, and rotation crops

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål usually lays its eggs in small groups inside the leaf sheath and midrib of rice plants by making an incision and inserting eggs inside the tissues.

We studied BPH oviposition on 52 common rice weeds, 17 wild rices, and 21 crop plants in no-choice tests. Five pair of 1-wk-old BPH adults were confined on young, potted test plants for 4 d. The test plants were examined for oviposition sites and egg hatching every day for 4 d after the first nymphs hatched. If nymphs did not appear, plants were examined with a microscope for unhatched eggs. We had the following results.

There was no oviposition on weeds *Chrysopogon aciculatus*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Eleocharis dulcis*, *Fimbristylis bisumbellata*, *F. miliacea*, *Cyperus kyllingia*, *Scirpus articulatus*, *S. supinus*, *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Cleome viscosa*, *Eclipta alba*, *Euphorbia hirta*, *Gomphrena celosioides*, *Marsilea* sp., *Trianthema portulacastrum*, and *Vernonia cinerea*. There was also none on crop plants Indian mustard and East Indian lemon grass.

Oviposition was inside the leaf sheath tissue on the following: weeds *Brachiaria ramosa*, *B. distachya*, *Dichanthium caricosum*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Echinochloa colona*, *E. stagnina*, *Eragrostis gangetica*, *E. pilosa*, *E. tenella*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Leersia perrieri*, *Leptochloa panicea*, *Panicum repens*, *Paspalum scrobiculatum*, *Paspalidium flavidum*, *Pennisetum pedicellatum*, *Rottboellia exaltata*, and *setaria pallide-fusca*; wild rices *Oryza alta*, *O. australiensis*, *O. barthii*, *O. eichingeri*, *O. collina*, *O. glaberrima*, *O.*

grandiglumis, *O. meyeriana* ssp. *granulata*, *O. latifolia*, *O. minuta*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinalis*, *O. perennis*, *O. punctata*, *O. ridleyi*, and *O. rufipogon*; and on crop plants wheat, barley, oats, finger millet, foxtail millet, koda millet, proso millet, little millet, and Japanese millet.

Oviposition was inside the stem tissue just below the flower head in the weeds *Cyperus compressus*, *C. difformis*, *C. distans*, *C. iria*, *C. rotundus*, and *C. tenuispica*.

The insect oviposited inside the tender stem tissue of the weeds *Bergia ammannioides*, *Commelina benghalensis*, *Heliotropium indicum*, *Hydrolea zeylanica*, *Ipomoea reptans*, *Ludwigia perennis*, and *Sphenoclea zeylanica*; and on crop plants maize, sorghum, pearl millet, peanut, mungbean, black gram, sunn hemp, and jute.

On crop plants sugarcane and napier grass, oviposition was inside the growing bud tissue.

The insect laid naked egg clusters on the leaf lamina of the weeds *Eleusine indica* and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. In these weeds the egg groups were deposited on the external surface of the leaf lamina in groups of 7-12, were visible (see figure), and hatched normally. This unusual behavior resulted in exposed eggs which may be available for predators, or contact with insecticides. Irrespective of the site and method of oviposition, all the eggs laid hatched normally at about the same time. □

BPH egg clusters on leaf lamina of a grass weed.

Occurrence of black bug in Tamil Nadu

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The black bug *Scotinophara lurida* was found in large numbers in 1984 Apr-Jul in Tiruchirapalli District, where about 4,000 ha of rices ADT36, Co 29, and BCPI are grown. There were more black bugs on ADT36 than on Co 29 and BCPI. The bug infested all varieties and caused bugburn in many fields. It infested the crop from 30 d after transplanting to harvest, during which time the population substantially increased. At late flowering stage the population averaged 20 bugs/hill.

Farmers indicated that black bug had regularly infested fields for 3 yr. In Jul-Sep, the insect infested about 800 ha. Farmers often don't see the bug because it lives at the base of the tillers.

Spraying 600 ml fenthion/ha controlled black bug. □

Gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzivora* H & G in Zambia

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GM has been reported in eight countries in Africa: Guinea Bissau, Senegal, Mali, Upper Volta, Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Cameroon, and Sudan. It is a localized pest of lowland irrigated rice except in Upper Volta where it is one of the most serious and widespread insect pests in irrigated and rainfed lowland rice.

In Apr 1984 IIRI and IITA organized a monitoring tour in Zambia and Tanzania. The tour group visited five rice projects in Zambia and observed GM in all lowland irrigated rice. GM incidence

was very high in Turners Asbestos Products Projects and at the National Irrigation Research Station.

The GM collected from Zambia was

identified as *Orseolia oryzivora* by the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London. This species was identified from the collections in the Lake Chilwa area of

Malawi in 1974. These findings suggest that GM is distributed throughout the Guinea savannas of Africa. □

Chemical control of grasshoppers in Pakistan

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In some years, grasshopper *Hieroglyphus* spp. cause significant losses to rice nurseries and crops in Pakistan. In 1982 we tested four dusts in doses generally recommended in treatments for grasshopper control at AARF.

Grasshoppers were collected from rice fields and reared at room temperature to achieve a large population of adults of uniform age and size. The dusts were cotton dust (6.3% BHC + 10.4% DDT + 83.3% sulfur), BHC 10%, 1:3 mixture of BHC 10% + DDT 10%, and carbaryl 10%. They were sprinkled on the grasshoppers and rice leaves. In the first trial, 100 grasshoppers were kept in a glass jar without food for 24 h, then were released on fresh food. In the second trial grasshoppers were caged on dusted leaves of

Grasshopper control with different insecticide dusts.^a AARF, Pakistan.

Dust	Dosage	Mortality (%) at indicated hours after treatment				
		1	3	6	12	24
	<i>g/100 grasshoppers</i>	<i>Direct dusting on grasshoppers</i>				
Cotton dust ^b	10	13.7	100	100	100	100
BHC 10%	10	22.3	100	100	100	100
BHC 10% + DDT 10% 1:3 mixture	10	18.0	100	100	100	100
Carbaryl 10%	10	16.3	100	100	100	100
Untreated control	—	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.6 ^a	0.0 ^a	1.3 ^a
LSD at 5%		7.4	20.9	21.3	28.6	16.8
	<i>kg ai/ha</i>	<i>Feeding on dust-impregnated nursery leaves</i>				
Cotton dust ^b	7.20	3.0	42.7	85.0	100	100
BHC 10%	0.75	8.7	49.7	88.3	100	100
BHC 10% + DDT 10% 1:3 mixture.	0.31 + 0.94	5.0	41.0	76.3	100	100
Carbaryl 10%	2.00	8.3	46.3	81.7	100	100
Untreated control	—	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.3 ^a	1.6 ^a	1.3 ^a
LSD at 5%		6.0	9.3	13.7	15.4	33.8

^aIn each column, averages followed by common letters are significantly similar at 95% level of confidence. ^bCotton dust is a brand name for the mixture of BHC + DDT + sulfur (3:5:40); the dose of 7.2 kg ai/ha is based on the 48% active ingredient in the formulation.

plants. Insect mortality was recorded 1, 3, 6, 12, and 24 h after treatment. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications.

With direct dusting, all grasshoppers died in 3 h. With foliar dusting, they died in 12 h. All the dusts were effective (see table). □

Entomophaga grylli destruction of locust *Oxya-hyla intricata* in Vietnam

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The fungus *E. grylli* (Fres.) Batko is the most common Entomophthorales fungus and often is associated with locust and grasshopper outbreaks. Data from Southeast Asia describe an outbreak of *E. grylli* in a *Patanga succinata* population on maize east of Lopburi Province in Thailand. By the end of the rainy season, the fungus had destroyed 90% of the locust population and was found in 9 other acridid pests in Thailand.

1. Germinating conidia of *E. grylli* on the wing of *O. intricata*
Scale = 10 µm.

O. intricata Stål is widely distributed in Southeast Asia — Burma, Thailand, Vietnam, West Malaysia — and some parts of South China. It damages rice and several other crops.

In autumn 1983, dense *O. intricata* populations seriously damaged rice around Hanoi, Vietnam. *E. grylli* infected 85-90% adults and nymphs, which died on the plants. Masses of conidiophores